

ISic0853

Funerary inscription for Klaudia Soteris

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

Limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Susan Walker

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Susan Walker

Autopsy

Walker 2015

Last Change

2018-02-08 - Jonathan Prag edited the file on the basis of draft of new edition by Susan Walker

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Salvatore Politi (ap. IG XIV.36) reports found next to the so-called 'tomb of Archimedes', a rock-cut tomb in the Grotticelli necropolis ; according to Wilshere (letter to De Rossi), 'da un fosso sulle confine di Caradicia (? illegible)

ed Epipoli'; according to Ferrua 1941 reporting De Rossi, 'trovata in una fossa tra Agradina e Tyche'.

Coordinates

37.078359, 15.281140

Current Location

Great Britain, Oxfordshire, Oxford, Ashmolean Museum, inventory AN2007.61

Physical Description

The stone is reconstructed from six fragments. The upper right corner is lost, as is a piece left of centre of the upper edge down into the second line of text, and smaller chips from the left edge and the lower right corner. The stone is filled with plaster extending from the lower left corner of the upper right break to the fourth line of text. The fragment below is stained red. The stone has been filled with plaster in all these breaks. It was not removed from its slate frame in 2012.

Dimensions

Height 18.6 cm

Width 25.2 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Greek text over 6 lines, becoming more compressed towards the end. The letters are very deeply cut with a bull-nosed chisel, and are painted in red.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

rhomboid omega, xsi in the form of zeta with a cross-bar, regular quadrate sigma and epsilon, and frequent use of letters in ligature

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 32 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. [Θ(εοῖς)] · Κ(αταχθονίοις)
2. Κ(λαυδία) · Σωτήρ[ρ]ις
3. χρηστὰ καὶ
4. ἄμεμπτὸς ἔζ(ησεν)
5. ἔτη · ζγ' · μῆ(νας) · γ' · ἡμέ(ρας) θ'

Apparatus

Σωτήρ[ις], Kaibel

κ[αὶ], Kaibel

ἔτη · ζγ' · μῆνας · ε', Webster

Translation (en)

To the nether gods, Claudia Soteris, good and blameless, lived 63 years, 3 months, 9 days

Commentary

Webster tentatively restored the name in line 2 as Quinta(?). The form of the opening sigma of Soteris is distorted by a vertical break in the stone.

Webster, following De Rossi and Wilshere, dated the inscription to the Byzantine period on grounds of palaeography, but it is surely pagan and of pre-Christian, Roman date, the distinctive letter forms (for example, rhomboid omega) being especially prevalent locally, while the formulaic epithet and the precise indication of age at death are typical of Greek epitaphs of modest quality made for people of relatively low social standing in early imperial Sicily. Indeed, similar epitaphs were found in situ by Orsi in the Grotticelli cemetery above cremation burials packed in ceramic jars; one such epitaph of a certain Valeria was associated with a large bronze coin of Trajan (Orsi 1913: 269, with fig.11) . However, late 19th-century exploration of the same cemetery had demonstrated that burials continued into the eighth century AD; some indubitably 4th-6th century finds of bronze jewellery and lamps were associated with fragmentary epitaphs of this type, which were surely residual (Orsi 1896: 346 for a fragment from the epitaph of Claudius, with rhomboid letter forms). Possibly this text was found broken in a late antique context of this sort.

For correspondence between De Rossi and Wilshere regarding the stone, see Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana VatLat 14273, 1885.339 (letter from Wilshere to De Rossi of May 20th 1885) and Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana VatLat 14273, 1885.509 (August 13th 1885). A tracing by Wilshere, sent to De Rossi, is held in the De Rossi Ms, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana Vat.Lat., 10529 (non vidimus)

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Bibliography

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- Webster, T.B.L. 1929. The Wilshere Collection at Pusey House in Oxford. *Journal of Roman Studies*. 19: 150-154. At 152 no.21
- Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 197-198 no.68 fig.34

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Photo Gower, courtesy Ashmolean museum